

The Deuteronomistic History

By Morganne Ottobre, Johns Hopkins University

Entry tags: Hebrew Bible, Biblical Prophets, Religious Group, Text, Israelite Religion, Religious History, Jewish Traditions, Judeans and Israelites

The so-called “Deuteronomistic History” is a scholarly category that groups the books of Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Samuel, and Kings for their similar terminology and theological orientation. Martin Noth is often credited with the “discovery” of the Deuteronomistic History, although connections between the various books had been noted by scholars long before Noth’s own synthesis (See the works of Wellhausen, de Wette, and Ewald). Noth defined the Deuteronomistic History as a history of the nations of Israel/Judah which articulated the theological reasons for Israel’s fall in 722BCE and Judah’s exile in 586BCE. The Judean scribe(s) behind this history maintain that God allowed – perhaps even orchestrated – the fall of Israel and Judah because the kings and the people neglected the terms of the covenant set forth in the book of Deuteronomy. However, scholars like Frank Moore Cross also found more positive themes expressed throughout the “history” such as God’s promise to always uphold the Davidic monarchy and the permanence of God’s presence in the temple in Jerusalem. Other themes that appear frequently throughout the “history” include warnings against idolatry, the importance of centralizing worship (at the Jerusalem temple), and the complicated nature of kingship. Along with these broad themes, the books within the “history” share certain terms and phraseology such as “going after other gods,” “the place the LORD will cause his name to dwell,” “walk in the ways of the LORD,” “keep the commandments/statues/testimonies/judgements of the LORD,” “doing good/evil in the eyes of the LORD,” and “for the sake of my servant David.” (See Weinfeld Appendix A for full list). Overall, the Deuteronomistic History appears to project a Judean perspective which favors the temple in Jerusalem, the Davidic monarchy, and the laws/ covenantal terms in the book of Deuteronomy. However, when analyzing these key phrases, terms, and theological perspectives, it is important to note that no book within the Deuteronomistic history is composed solely of Deuteronomistic themes/phrases, meaning the books themselves remain quite distinct. Moreover, each book employs these themes/phrases in different ways and in different quantities. For example, Deuteronomistic language appears heavily in texts that describe key moments in the history of Israel/Judah. These include the fall of the Northern Kingdom (2 Kings 17), the construction of the Jerusalem temple (1 Kings 8), the establishment of the Davidic monarchy (1 Samuel 12/2 Samuel 7), the reign of Josiah and the discovery of the “Law” (2 Kings 22), and the fall of Judah (2 Kings 23-25). The books of Judges and Joshua by contrast, contain very little Deuteronomistic phrases/themes, and the language that does appear occurs only in transition points or in speeches (see portions of Judges 1-2, 6, 10, 19-21, and Joshua 23). Thus, it is important to remember that the Deuteronomistic History is merely a scholarly category used to describe the phenomena of shared terms, phrases, and themes across different texts in the Hebrew Bible. There remain large divisions within the field regarding the scope, dating, and even existence of the Deuteronomistic History as a unified scribal enterprise. Please see the bibliography for theories concerning dating the Deuteronomistic History and theories concerning its history of composition and redaction.

Date Range: 700 BCE - 300 BCE

Region: Ancient Judah

Region tags: Eastern Mediterranean, Levant, Israel, Palestine

Ancient Judah at its greatest extent (South and West borders particularly flexible)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Noth, Martin . Überlieferungsgeschichtliche Studien. Die Sammelnden Und Bearbeitenden Geschichtswerke Im Alten Testament. . Darmstadt: Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft, 1967. English translation: The Deuteronomistic History. 2nd ed. JSOTSup 15. Sheffield: Sheffield Academic Press, 1991.

– Source 2: Cross, Frank. "The Themes of the Book of Kings and the Structure of the Deuteronomistic History." In Canaanite Myth Hebrew Epic. Cambridge, Mass: Harvard University Press, 1973.

– Source 3: Kelle, Brad E., and Brent A. Strawn, eds. The Oxford Handbook of the Historical Books of the Hebrew Bible. Oxford University Press, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190261160.001.0001>.

Reference: Weinfeld, Moshe. Deuteronomy and the Deuteronomic School. Oxford: Clarendon Press, 1972.

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: This answer is referring to the books of Deuteronomy-Kings as there is no "Deuteronomistic History" stand-alone text

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

–Other textile: Parchment

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-ionic images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown

Materiality

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Many scholars believe the earlier redactions of the Deuteronomistic History (created during the reigns of Josiah and/or Hezekiah) may have been supported by the Judean monarchy given the "history's" tendency to support Davidic kings and the Jerusalem temple. However, not all scholars agree there was ever a version of the Deuteronomistic history composed before the exile. If the "history" is a product of the exilic or post exilic periods, there would have been no polity to fund its creation.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely elite Judean or post-exilic communities.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While the books of Deuteronomy-Kings are now considered "official religious scripture" by both Jewish and Christian communities, the term "scripture" is anachronistic when considering the communities that produced and transmitted these texts in ancient Judah. These were likely important religious and political texts, but it is unlikely these texts were considered "scripture" or "unalterable" until after the Second temple period.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While Biblical Hebrew is now considered a distinctly religious/sacred language, at the time of the composition of Deuteronomy-Kings it likely reflected a literary/religious register or a language similar to the spoken vernacular.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?

– Yes

↳ Food?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Sacred objects?

– No

↳ Daily life objects?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

↳ Incest

– Yes

- ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - No
- ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: See especially 1 Kings 21
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

|

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?
– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– Yes

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– I don't know

↳ Political failure?
– Yes

↳ Defeat in battle?
– Yes

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– Yes

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– Yes

- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?
 - Yes
- ↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Age of extant version of text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Content of text?
 - No
 - ↳ Ritual purpose of text?
 - No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– Yes

↳ Are there formal institutions merged with the state or polity of the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there an institutionalized police force whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– No

↳ Is there an institutionalized judicial system whose behavior is dictated by the legal code?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Deuteronomy presents a legal code, but it is unclear to what extent this legal code was enforced or reflective of the actual judicial system in Judah.

↳ Does the text in question specify institutionalized punishment?

– No

↳ Are there any established institutionalized rewards specified in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: The Deuteronomistic History is itself a collection of texts.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: Canonization is a later concept that does not apply to these ancient texts until after the Second Temple Period.

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– Yes

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

↳ Consists of good luck?

– I don't know

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– Yes

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– Yes

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– I don't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– Yes

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– I don't know

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– I don't know

↳ Moderation/frugality

– I don't know

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– I don't know

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– I don't know

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– I don't know

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– I don't know

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– I don't know

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– I don't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– I don't know

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Notes: Moses is buried in Deut 34, but the text is very vague. In the book of Kings, many kings are described as "resting with their ancestors" which many scholars associate with secondary burial in a family or royal tomb.

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The relationship between Yahweh and the king in the Deuteronomistic history is incredibly complicated - see the Law of the King in Deuteronomy 17:14-20, 1 Samuel 8, 2 Samuel 7, and the refrain in Judges 19-21 "in those days Israel had no king."

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: A good king was the extension of God's justice on earth, but this was rarely the case.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Can reward
– Yes
- ↳ Can punish
– Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Notes: Worship of other gods or worship at sacred sites outside of the temple at Jerusalem is considered illicit worship by the Deuteronomistic History.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: God communicates with prophets (books of Kings, Samuel, and Judges), judges/leaders (Joshua, Judges, Samuel, Kings), with the monarch (Samuel and Kings), as well as with regular people (Judges 16 - Samson's parents, for example). God communicates in broad daylight, through dreams, through miraculous deeds, through visions, and through divinity means like lots and the Urim and Thummim.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There is one exception, in 1 Samuel 28 Saul consults a necromancer at Endor who revives Samuel's spirit and enables Samuel's spirit to communicate to Saul. The story paints Saul in a very negative light and Samuel is not happy to have been disturbed.

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: These beings include angels/messengers of God (Judges 13) and members of a divine counsel (1 Kings 22).

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

↳ In dreams?

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession?

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices?

– I don't know

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Only one text (1 Kings 22) within the Deuteronomistic History explicitly suggests a pantheon or divine counsel. It is not a belief/motif carried consistently through the "history."

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– I don't know

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)

– No

↳ Divination through human communication?

– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?

– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Most are men, but there are several important female prophets (Deborah and Huldah).

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– No

↳ Is physical ordeal required?

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: Urim and Thummim, lots

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– I don't know

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: incense offerings

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings?
(I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

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Beliefs

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↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Notes: The relationship between Yahweh and the king in the Deuteronomistic history is incredibly complicated - see the Law of the King in Deuteronomy 17:14-20, 1 Samuel 8, 2 Samuel 7, and the refrain in Judges 19-21 "in those days Israel had no king."

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: A good king was the extension of God's justice on earth, but this was rarely the case.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

|

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– No

Notes: Worship of other gods or worship at sacred sites outside of the temple at Jerusalem is considered illicit worship by the Deuteronomistic History.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: God communicates with prophets (books of Kings, Samuel, and Judges), judges/leaders (Joshua, Judges, Samuel, Kings), with the monarch (Samuel and Kings), as well as with regular people (Judges 16 - Samson's parents, for example). God communicates in broad daylight, through dreams, through miraculous deeds, through visions, and through divinity means like lots and the Urim and Thummim.

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Notes: There is one exception, in 1 Samuel 28 Saul consults a necromancer at Endor who revives Samuel's spirit and enables Samuel's spirit to communicate to Saul. The story paints Saul in a very negative light and Samuel is not happy to have been disturbed.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: These beings include angels/messengers of God (Judges 13) and members of a divine counsel (1 Kings 22).

- ↳ Supernatural beings can be seen
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life?
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ In trance possession?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices?
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists?
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Only one text (1 Kings 22) within the Deuteronomistic History explicitly suggests a pantheon or divine counsel. It is not a belief/motif carried consistently through the "history."

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra (animal remains)
– No

↳ Divination through human communication?
– Yes

↳ Human being the vehicle for the oracle?
– Yes

↳ Human being the interpreter of the oracle?
– Yes

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified sex/gender?

– No

Notes: Most are men, but there are several important female prophets (Deborah and Huldah).

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of specified class?

– No

↳ Is sex-deprivation required?

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required?

– No

↳ Is physical ordeal required?

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior?

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material?

– Other [specify]: Urim and Thummim, lots

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– Yes

↳ Libations?
– Yes

↳ Food?
– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?
– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?
– No

↳ Sacred objects?
– No

↳ Daily life objects?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
– Yes

↳ Food
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s)
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery
 - Yes
 - ↳ Incest
 - Yes
 - ↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)
 - No
 - ↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - I don't know

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - Yes
 - Notes: See especially 1 Kings 21
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of bad luck?
 - I don't know

- ↳ Political failure?
 - Yes
- ↳ Defeat in battle?
 - Yes
- ↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
 - Yes
- ↳ Disaster on journeys?
 - Yes
- ↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Sickness or illness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Impaired reproduction?
 - Yes
- ↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
 - Yes

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done only by high god
 - Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - Yes
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
 - Yes
- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - I don't know
- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - Yes
- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - Yes

- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
– Yes
- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
– Yes
- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
– I don't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
– Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
– Yes

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - I don't know
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - I don't know
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - I don't know
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - I don't know
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - I don't know
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - I don't know
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - I don't know

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– I don't know

↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– Yes

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness
– I don't know

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

Monogamy (females)

– Yes

Other sexual constraints (males)

– No

Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– Yes

↳ Are sacrifices specified by the text?

– Yes

↳ Animal sacrifice?

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifice?

– No

↳ Are there self-sacrifices specified by the text?

– No

↳ Are there material offerings present?

– Yes

↳ Are they mandatory?

– Yes

↳ Are they composed of valuable objects?

– I don't know

↳ Are they composed of daily-life objects?

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches)?

– I don't know

↳ Are there particular smells associated with material offerings?

– Yes

Notes: incense offerings

↳ Are there particular visual stimuli (colors, symbols) associated with the offerings? (I.e. 'must be bright' 'must include red')

– No

↳ Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory?

– Yes

↳ By the community?

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals?

– Yes

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Unknown. As the Deuteronomistic History was likely completed in stages, it may have begun under the nation of Judah and was completed under the Yehud province. It may also be the sole work of the Yehud province.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Perhaps religious elites working in/for the Temple.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The text does advocate general wisdom (see 1 Kings 3).

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Unknown. As the Deuteronomistic History was likely completed in stages, it may have begun under the nation of Judah and was completed under the Yehud province. It may also be the sole work of the Yehud province.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Perhaps religious elites working in/for the Temple.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

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Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: The text does advocate general wisdom (see 1 Kings 3).

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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